

Neo-Assyrian Healers (āšipu/mašmaššu-exorcists)

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Assyrian Religions, Mesopotamian Religions, Religious Practice, Near East, Babylonian Religions, Mesopotamian Religion

The exorcist (Akkadian āšipu/mašmaššu) acted in an intellectual community as one of five main scholarly professions throughout the Neo-Assyrian period. Exorcists were primarily concerned with medical and magical healing, as well as diagnosing causes of illness, for private - and frequently highborn - clients. Furthermore, they could perform rituals for the city, temples, and the court. Accordingly, they were often connected to the royal court, as well as official and religious institutions in various cities. However, exorcists were not priests. Among the tools of their trade were numerous rituals, medical remedies, prayers, and incantations. Exorcists in the Neo-Assyrian period did not distinguish between what we today label as “magic” and “medicine”, instead believing that most illnesses were caused by supernatural forces, such as gods or demons. Once a patient was seized by an illness, healing could be achieved through identifying the ailment and the agent causing the malady, and subsequently applying therapeutic or ritual treatments to cure the illness and its symptoms, as well as ritual actions to appease the god in question. Healing therefore consisted of both medical and magical treatments, and the term encapsulates the combined focus in the exorcist’s methods for diagnosing and treating illness as well as ensuring social, physical, or mental wellbeing. Although an exorcist’s duties partially overlapped with those of the physician (asû) and diviner (bārû), the exorcist appears to have been the primary professional practicing a broad selection of traditional Assyrian and Babylonian healing methods in the Neo-Assyrian period. Accordingly, the translation “exorcist” is inadequate and often incorrect in describing his competences and duties. The majority of sources from this period can be dated roughly to the 8th and 7th centuries BCE, and they were excavated in the royal text collections at Nineveh, a temple library in Kalhu (Nimrud), private libraries in Assur (especially the “Haus des Beschwörungspriesters”), and a private text collection from Huzirina (Sultantepe).

Date Range: 900 BCE - 612 BCE

Region: Cities integrated in the Assyrian empire

Region tags: Middle East, Mesopotamia

In the cities integrated in the Assyrian empire, especially the main cities of Kalhu (Nimrud), Nineveh and Assur, but also in Babylonia and the cities in S. Mesopotamia.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Jean, C. 2006: La magie néo-Assyrienne en contexte - Recherches sur le metier d'exorciste et le concept d'āšipūtu (State Archives of Assyria Studies 17; Helsinki: The Neo-Assyrian Text Corpus Project)
- Source 2: Arbøll, T. P. 2020: Medicine in Ancient Assur - A Microhistorical Study of the Neo-Assyrian

Healer Kišir-Aššur (Ancient Magic and Divination 18; Leiden and Boston: Brill)

– Source 3: Robson, E. 2019: Ancient Knowledge Networks. A Social Geography of Cuneiform Scholarship in First-Millennium Assyria and Babylonia (London: UCL Press)

Notes: Arbøll and Robson are available online with open access

– Source 1: Böck, B. 2014: The Healing Goddess Gula - Towards an Understanding of Ancient Babylonian Medicine (Culture and History of the Ancient Near East 67; Leiden, Boston: Brill)

– Source 2: Geller, M. J. 2010: Ancient Babylonian Medicine - Theory and Practice (Malden, Oxford, and Chichester: Wiley-Blackwell)

– Source 3: Heeßel, N. P. 2000: Babylonisch-assyrische Diagnostik (Alter Orient und Altes Testament 43; Münster: Ugarit-Verlag)

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <http://oracc.museum.upenn.edu/cams/gkab/>

– Source 1 Description: The Geography of Knowledge

– Source 2 URL: <http://oracc.museum.upenn.edu/cams/akno/>

– Source 2 Description: Ancient Knowledge Networks online

– Source 3 URL: <http://oracc.museum.upenn.edu/saao/knpp/>

– Source 3 Description: Knowledge and Power in the Neo-Assyrian Empire

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <http://oracc.museum.upenn.edu/saao/saa10/>

– Source 1 Description: Letters from Assyrian and Babylonian Scholars

– Source 2 URL: <http://oracc.museum.upenn.edu/asbp/ninmed/>

– Source 2 Description: The Nineveh Medical Project

– Source 3 URL: <http://oracc.museum.upenn.edu/cmawro/>

– Source 3 Description: Corpus of Mesopotamian Anti-witchcraft Rituals online

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: The group known as physicians (asû) may have competed with exorcists over influence in relation to healing, though the exact differences between the two professions in the Neo-

Assyrian period are not always clear. Further information can be found in the background literature. Nonetheless, competition can generally be observed among the scholars of various disciplines at the Nineveh court in especially the 7th century BCE.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):
– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):
– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:
– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:
– No

Does the religion have official political support
– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:
– Yes

Notes: Only in part. The exorcists' influence, and by extension their available resources, often came through patrons, such as kings, the elite, or offices held in temples. Nonetheless, individuals who received healing likely paid cuts of meats or similar gifts in return for services.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:
– No

Notes: Though the reconstruction of temples etc. was funded by the state, these structures cannot be considered the religious infrastructure of the exorcists alone.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:
– Yes

Notes: The Assyrian king was the chief priest of the main deity Aššur. The exorcists were part of this religious system, though not clergy members as such in most instances.

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

Notes: Only the case of the king contains this inherent duality.

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Not onto people of different faiths, though the polity takes part in various rituals.

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Seeing as much political propaganda contains references to myths and includes divine favour, the overarching legal settings enforced by the polity must resonate within the religious code. However, further proof is needed to answer confidently.

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Notes: In relation to, for example, temples.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral

scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: Not true scripture, but individual texts or text series considered authoritative (not sacred). However, extraneous texts were also considered and used by exorcists.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: There are shorter stories explaining how individual pieces of text came to be. Overall, the exorcist's corpus of texts is attributed to the god Ea, though this information is not found in a story.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Exorcists copied (parts of) the Erra Epic in this period, and this piece of literature originated as a dream revealed to the author by a god.

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– Yes

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Most scholars received extensive training in their own professional corpus, as well as experience in working with other disciplines. Their corpora consisted of ritual, magical, medical, early scientific texts, myths, laments, etc. - I would not classify it formally as scriptures.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: Exorcists were regularly connected to temples, and although they were not priests, monumental religious architecture did play a role in relation to this profession.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: At least one private tomb is known from the "Haus des Beschwörungspriesters" (N4 text collection) in Assur. The exorcists may have held a role in relation to the royal burials (kings were buried in the palace in Assur, queens in the north-west palace in Nimrud).

↳ Cemeteries:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Ziggurat (stepped, multi-terraced temple tower)

Notes: Any role exorcists may have had in connection to this type of building is unclear

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– Some public spaces

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Also available in temples, though they were not necessarily public in all areas.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– No

Notes: Iconography was shared within Assyrian religion.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– No

Notes: Although some ghosts can roam within the world

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: Ghosts can roam the earth

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: The treatment of a corpse was likely the same among people in the Assyrian elite

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Field doesn't know

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Found in some graves not necessarily belonging to exorcists

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Found in some graves not necessarily belonging to exorcists

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Found in some graves not necessarily belonging to exorcists

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Found in some graves not necessarily belonging to exorcists

↳ Other grave goods:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Found in some graves not necessarily belonging to exorcists

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Most exorcists would have been buried in the family homes, though it is unclear to which extent the burial itself would have been a formal event outside of the family. Certainly it included rituals.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: A diverse pantheon existed, though the deity Aššur was supreme in Assyria.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: The king was the chief priest of Aššur.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Food offerings are presented to Aššur in his temple in the city Assur.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Many prescriptions specify that a patient sees a ghost in dreams, but others simply state that he continually sees dead people.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Ghosts often scream in the ears of a patient causing symptoms.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Can be invoked through necromancy

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: Presumably, seeing as ghosts and demons can affect you outside.

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Can cause illness.

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: They eat clay and drink mud in the underworld, which is why regular offerings sweeten their afterlives.

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Frequent cause of disease and death - burial is essential (for example, king Sargon II died on the battlefield, and because his corpse was not retrieved the court had to abandon his capital Dur-Sharrukin/Khorsabad).

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Notes: Communication to the extent that they most often appear or make noises

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

Notes: Necromancy

↳ Only through specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Necromancy required a specialist it seems, though ghosts will afflict disease upon people, which the specialists then cure.

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: By causing illness and physical symptoms

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Most often, demons are hidden, but in a few cases the patient believes he sees who has seized him.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: When they touch, seize, hit, etc. a patient, the evil in question can be felt because it causes illness.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: They can certainly protect, though reward is unclear.

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: A person in close contact with one afflicted by a demonic being could likely be influenced indirectly through that patient's inauspicious state.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: They can be protective

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: They can be evil and cause disease

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: We often read that they devour, i.e., cause pain, to an area of the patient's body.

In that sense they are described as having hunger.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: We know a variety of physical descriptions of these, so their forms were known to healing specialists, at least.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The exorcist could take on the appearance of semi-divine beings, such as the apkallu-sage. Furthermore, at least one Assyrian king was described as having been brought up by a goddess, but he was not considered divine as such. Semi-divine humans, such as Gilgamesh, are known, but not from the Neo-Assyrian period.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Notes: Not exclusively, and occasionally with confused kinship

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: Not always strict hierarchy

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Demons operated within more than one domain. Some were able to roam freely if they were not stopped. Protective deities operated within specific contexts.

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

- ↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:
Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:
– Yes
 - ↳ Food:
– Yes
 - ↳ Sacred space(s):
– Yes
 - ↳ Sacred object(s):
– Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
– Yes [specify]: Various actions performed can be the taboo of several gods
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
– Field doesn't know
Notes: It becomes more tricky here, as murder in a foreign land, e.g., while on campaign, is less likely to have incurred divine wrath. Murder within Assyria in a city was problematic.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
– Yes
 - ↳ Adultery:
– Yes

↳ Incest:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other sexual practices:
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
– Yes
Notes: One has to swear to a divine symbol or similarly in, for example, a trial.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
– Yes
Notes: One of the main diseases was *māmītu*, which could mean "oath" and "curse".

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
– Yes
Notes: Tricky because divine beings were called upon when people performed sorcery. However, the same deities could be used to revert the sorcery and send the problems back to the witch/warlock.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
– Yes
Notes: Rituals regularly concern slander.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As people regularly swore in trials, it could imply that deities cared about property crimes.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: Purification rites were used and administered by exorcists, so we must assume that some aspects of personal hygiene were relevant for engaging with the divine.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: It is rarely known to begin with, but identifying the cause for a patient was one of the obligations of the exorcist

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Ghosts and witchcraft also cause disease. Some illnesses were regarded as punishment for an unknown transgression etc.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Though not always; most often the reason has to be identified by the exorcist or diviner (bārû). By extension, the reason for punishment was not known to begin with. The symptoms of illness, for example, were signs that something was wrong and should be examined by a specialist.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: Poorly performed rituals could cause divine anger

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done randomly:

– Yes

Notes: In some cases demons just latched onto you in the street.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: E.g., broken oaths could cause disease; poor leadership could ensure a deity('s statue) would be removed from a city, thereby causing crisis.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: Good luck could be gained from visiting a deity's temple

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Though not infinite
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Social norms are reflected in some rituals performed by this group, as such, the group transmits these. The exorcists do not compose them, however, as the norms are found throughout Assyria.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: The exorcist Kisir-Ashur/Kiřir-Ařřur from the city Assur came from a family of exorcists, and these individuals must have had wives.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Periodic fasting cannot be excluded

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: There are food taboos, though only in certain contexts.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Yes

Notes: It is important to be clear that human sacrifices were *not* practiced as such. However, the royal ritual known as "the substitute king ritual" required a substitute king (most likely a prisoner of war or a poor person) to be king for a period of time before being sent to his appointed fate, i.e., death. Additionally, there are one or two references to people with very specific and severe medical conditions being killed.

↳ Foreign, slaves:

– Yes

↳ Commoners:

– Yes

↳ Elites:

– No

↳ Other:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Yes

Notes: Yes in the sense that the exorcists performed house calls to patients, and they were therefore exposed to whatever afflicted the patients.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: The same ethical precepts known among the elites and citizens of Assyria proper.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Most rituals performed by the exorcists were intended for small-scale performance for individual patients.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Several such rituals are known, but some are periodical, such as the New Year celebrations

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Schools of thought, and thereby interpretation of texts, likely differed between some families, and they could differ between specialists in cities or regions

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There does not appear to be such markers, but there is a degree of uncertainty because there is much we do not know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Notes: Overall no, when employing kinship terminology, e.g., in colophons, they generally describe actual familial relationships. Still, it was not uncommon in some ancient Mesopotamian traditions to use "father/son" to describe relationships of power.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Perhaps in the sense that they may have performed rituals on behalf of the city in connection to famine.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Ritual specialists and scholars besides exorcists were likely involved in rituals in connection to widespread famine.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No true poverty relief, though patron relationships could help an exorcist to receive food and clothes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is clear some elderly people were treated by the exorcists, but it cannot be characterised directly as institutionalised care.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: All exorcists were religious professionals

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– No

Notes: As far as I know, only male exorcists are known from the Neo-Assyrian period. In fact, the only reference to a female exorcist (āšiptu) may be in the anti-witchcraft ritual Maqlû in a list of sorceresses.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Many scholars, including exorcists, likely received training in other disciplines within other family homes. The teachers were often part of another elite profession of scholarship, and these families were part of a network of scholars. In most cases, these were not institutions as such, though they represent other educational environments.

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– No

Notes: Presumably no, as far as I know. Yet one royal woman at least was likely involved in scribal training.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Especially in temples. It cannot be excluded that the exorcists were involved in some unknown capacity in the bureaucracy of some temples.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Some exorcists with official offices in temples could have received food there, but it was not a public food storage.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: The exorcists regularly held or inherited offices in temples, from which they may have received an income.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group members were expected to perform corvée labour for the state each year

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: They must have interacted with people in positions with the power to arrest etc., but to which

extent it can be characterised as an institutionalised police force is unclear.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Judicial matters could be resolved by councils in the city or higher up in the chain of governance. As such it was not a single, clearcut institution providing the judicial system.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Punishment were surely administered, though the majority known from legal documents relate to economic matters, such as inheritance or debt. Considering previous law codes, it seems likely that punishments could be physical, and they might have included execution.

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Field doesn't know

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Field doesn't know

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Field doesn't know

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Field doesn't know

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: They share laws with other members of the Assyrian community. A number of formal legal codes exist from previous periods, though a Neo-Assyrian one as such has not been uncovered.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Exorcists were likely brought on military campaigns, so in that sense some travelled with the Assyrian army.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: People living in Assyria would generally have been formally protected by the Assyrian army.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: Many rituals were written in complicated writing, which exorcists would have been specialists in reading. But it cannot be considered a distinct written language.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Cuneiform writing was available throughout society especially to the elite. Additionally, Aramaic was used widely towards the end of the Neo-Assyrian period, and it cannot be excluded that exorcists would have used this for day-to-day communication.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Cuneiform writing was available throughout society, especially for the elite, and exorcists used this for their professional texts and for other communication. Additionally, Aramaic was used widely

towards the end of the Neo-Assyrian period, and it cannot be excluded that exorcists would have used this for day-to-day communication.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The same calendar used throughout Assyria

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Notes: It cannot be excluded that some exorcists had a small food production in connection to their family home.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Exorcists received food from patients upon having performed healing rituals, they likely have received food from offices they held in temples, and they may have received food via patrons whom they served.

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Patoralism

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: Others may have applied as well, though in most cases, we do not know the origin of their food.

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